

IMPROVEMENTS IN THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ELECTRICITY AND HEAT CONSUMPTION IN AN INTEGRATED MILL PRODUCING PULP AND PAPER

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Abstract

Due to pronounced volatility of energy prices and rise of environmental requirements, European governments and industrial companies are forced to identify effective ways of increasing energy utilization efficiency. The pulp and paper industry is characterised by its large energy requirements. In this study, a paper machine belonging to one of the largest pulp and paper mill in Slovakia was analysed by means of material and energy balances elaboration. Potential savings proposals focused on steam savings and optimisation of electrical energy consumption in the sections of stock preparation and paper drying were considered and further analysed. By means of the proposed improved heat conservation, steam consumption decrease of the paper machine can be achieved and the saved steam can be used for boosting the electricity production in the paper mill's central rating and power plant. The increased in-house electricity production and the consequent lower overall electricity import of the paper mill can lead to a decrease of electricity production in a marginal source (most likely a thermal power plant) and subsequently to a reduction of global CO₂ emissions. Finally, calculations of economic profitability and preliminary feasibility study of presented measures have been performed. The results indicate that the presented set of measures can save approximately 10% in heat consumption and up to 2% in electricity consumption of the entire paper machine.

Introduction

Increasing energy utilization efficiency represents very important variable in energy policy of European Union. Pulp and paper industry is one of the largest industrial energy users worldwide and belongs to the largest industry segments in Slovak Republic. Energy demands of papermaking operations, such as stock preparation and paper drying, account for more than a half of the operational costs of the paper mill. Efforts with various degrees of complexity have been continuously directed at reducing energy costs of paper mills^{1,2}. An integrated mill producing pulp and paper usually consists of four main sections – wood preparation, fibre line, paper machine, storage of products. In the wood preparation section, raw wood is mechanically transformed into wood chips. In the fibre line section, pulp is extracted from wood chips through chemical, mechanical or combined processes and pulp fibres are generated. The final product of fibre line section is called stock and presents feed stream for a paper machine. In the paper machine, stock preparation (or so called “wet end process”) and paper dewatering take place. The stock preparation includes stock mixing, cleaning, deaeration, screening, refining and addition of chemicals, such as starch and additives for dyeing and fibre strengthening. In the paper dewatering process, there are three stages: web forming, pressing and drying. In the web forming stage, the stock is evenly distributed across perforated wire. The driving force in the web forming stage is the effect of gravitation. A continuous web enters the pressing section where water is removed by mechanical compression. One of the most important process parameters in mechanical dewatering of paper is the stock temperature which affects the viscosity of water. A reduction in viscosity lowers the friction, so that dryness of paper increases³. Thanks to mechanical dewatering processes, more than 98% of water present in stock is removed. Remaining water has to be removed in drying section by evaporation. The drying section is usually divided into two segments – predrying and afterdrying. Between these segments, water solution of modified starch is added. The source of heat required for evaporation is in the form of steam and preheated drying air. The parameters of steam and drying air are the key process variables in the paper drying operation^{4,5}.

Current operating status

In this work, a paper machine belonging to one of the largest pulp and paper mill in Slovak Republic was analysed by means of material and energy balances elaboration. The investigated paper machine consisted of conventional papermaking processes including stock mixing and pumping, fibre refining, web forming, pressing and drying. The available values of heat and electricity consumptions in previous years are summarized in Table I. The consumption of heat and electricity slightly increased in year 2014 because of continual increase in paper production. The heat source of paper machine was steam from extraction condensing steam turbine with average temperature of 157 °C and pressure of 0.49 MPa in monitored period (Figure 1). If steam was used in process heating, the heat produced from 1 tonne was in the area of 2.2 GJ. If steam remained in

condensing steam turbine, the average specific production of electrical energy achievable in steam turbine was 0.125 MWh per 1 tonne of this steam. Time record of overall steam flow for entire paper machine including stock preparation and paper dewatering section in monitored period is depicted in Figure 2. Produced paper weight in monitored period varied from 60 to 90 g/m² (Figure 3). The energy audit was focused on processes with largest energy requirements – paper dewatering, drying air ventilation and stock pumping and mixing. The possible use of low-temperature heat from adjacent operation units was also taken in account and further analysed.

Table I

Consumption of heat and electricity by paper machine in 2013 and 2014

Year	Heat consumption (10 ³ GJ)	Electricity consumption (10 ³ MWh)
2013	715	77
2014	718	78

Figure 1. Steam temperature and pressure time record

Figure 2. Overall steam flow time record

Figure 3. Paper weight time record

Paper drying and drying air ventilation

The paper drying section of analysed paper machine was divided into three sections. In the first section, the paper from mechanical dewatering entered the predrying section (PDS). To the paper from PDS was added water solution of starch in the sizing section. Part of the extra water added with starch solution was then removed in afterdrying section (ADS). The paper dryness after mechanical dewatering and paper moisture after individual drying sections was monitored and recorded (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Water content in paper in different stages of dewatering

This part of energy audit was focused on optimising the drying process. The main process that took place in this process is evaporation of water present in paper. Paper drying is associated with both heat and mass transfer. The drying air receives the water vapour evaporated from the paper. Therefore, its temperature and humidity were investigated further. The measured data of drying air supply in PDS and ADS are summarized in Table II. The source of drying air for PDS was fresh air from outside. The fresh air for PDS was preheated in series of heat exchangers by exhaust drying air from PDS, condensate, flash steam and steam. The drying air for ADS was the combination of outside air and indoor ambient air in volume ratio 1:1. This air was preheated also in series of heat exchangers, but only by exhaust drying air from ADS and flash steam. The unusually low absolute humidity of ADS exhaust air was caused by permanent shutdown of several drying cylinders in ADS. This was

the consequence of various technology improvements in the past. The recommended values of air parameters for paper drying process are stated in Table III^{3,5,6}. Another significant process parameter affecting the efficiency of paper drying process is the mass flow ratio of inlet drying air to exhaust drying air (usually called zero point). The optimal value of this parameter varies from 0.6 to 0.7⁶.

Table II
Parameters of inlet and exhaust drying air in PDS and ADS

Parameter	PDS inlet	PDS exhaust	ADS inlet	ADS exhaust
Absolute humidity (g H ₂ O / kg dry air)	60	140	40	75
Temperature (°C)	105	80	85	70
Volume flow (10 ³ m ³ /h)	140	300	60	120
Electricity consumption of air fans (kW)	183		59	

Table III
Recommended values of drying air parameters

Absolute humidity (g H ₂ O / kg dry air)	Relative humidity (%)	Temperature (°C)
150-200 (max. 250)	45-65 (max. 70)	80 - 100

The individual parameters were adjusted to satisfy recommended conditions of paper drying process (Table IV). The absolute humidity of ADS exhaust air is lower than recommended value because of relative humidity limitations. As presented in Table IV, the volume flow of air supply decreased in PDS and ADS by ca. 36 % and 58 %, respectively. The direct impact of this decrease is reduction of electricity consumptions of fans. In the case of PDS fans, the consumption decreased by 66 kW. In the case of ADS fans, the consumption decreased by 30 kW. The optimised air supply in drying process allowed reducing steam consumption in PDS and flash steam consumption in ADS. The flash steam saved in ADS preheating system replaced steam in paper machine heating system. The overall steam savings were in the area of 1900 kg/h.

Table IV

Parameter	PDS inlet	PDS exhaust	ADS inlet	ADS exhaust
Absolute humidity (g H ₂ O / kg dry air)	60	200	40	169
Temperature (°C)	105	80	85	70
Volume flow (10 ³ m ³ /h)	90	190	25	50
Electricity consumption of air fans (kW)	117		29	

Use of low-temperature heat from fibre line

In the paper mill, specifically in the fibre line, there was an excess of hot water with temperature of ca. 60 °C. This water could be used in the process of stock dilution what could increase the stock temperature. The rise of temperature level in paper machine obviously results in better conditions for mechanical dewatering of stock because of lower viscosity of water³. The increase of stock temperature by 5 – 10 °C could result in the minimum increase in paper dryness after mechanical dewatering section by 1 %^{3,7,8}. However, the upper temperature limit of stock was 60 °C, determined by experiences of operation personnel with limescale creation. As depicted in Figure 4, the average paper dryness after mechanical dewatering was approximately 47 %. The average stock temperature was below 50 °C. The increase of stock temperature to approximately 55 °C could increase the paper dryness after mechanical dewatering to 48 %. The potential effect of such measure on PDS is quantified in Table V. The decrease of amount of evaporated water in PDS resulted in the decrease of required amount of steam. The different values of heat of vaporization of water present in paper and steam used in drying cylinders contributed to the fact that each kg of evaporated water required between 1.1 and 1.6 kg of steam. Therefore, in the worst scenario (maximum drying efficiency), steam savings achieved

by proposed measure would be 800 kg/h. According to assumptions in the overview of current operating status, the foreseeable heat saving was 1.8 GJ/h. In addition, the saved steam could generate additional electric power in condensing steam turbine in the area of 100 kW. The additional effect of stock temperature increase was elimination of storage tank heating in winter, where another 1700 kg/h of steam was saved.

Table V

Calculated effect of stock temperature increase for representative paper weight 70 g/m²

	Dry solids (10 ³ kg/h)	Paper dryness after mechanical dewatering (%)	Evaporated water (10 ³ kg/h)
Before the measure	16.7	47	18.4
After the measure	16.7	48	17.7
Difference	0	+1	-0.7

Other measures

The other measures not discussed in previous sections were – the pressure regulation in fibre refining, the optimisation of stock mixing after refining and the use of hot water from adjacent compressor room. In the section of fibre refining, the pressure required for successful refining was adjusted by recycling of refined stock. The recycle of treated stock practically meant waste of energy supplied by pumps. The pump had already installed frequency converters, so the shutdown of stock recycling was possible immediately. The optimisation of stock mixing after refining consisted of agitator's optimal timing. The stock was stored after refining in two tanks depending on the source of wood. The residence times of stock were very low and continuous operation of agitators was not necessary. The proposed optimisation lied in timing of agitators operation. Operational experiments were conducted in order to quantify the effect of proposed energy saving measures. Adjacent compressor room presented suitable source of hot water. Because the paper machine was not self-sufficient in terms of hot water use, part of the cold water had to be heated by steam. The replacement of part of the cold water with hot water from compressor room resulted in decrease of steam requirements. The results of proposed energy saving measures are summarized in Table VI.

Table VI

Effects of proposed energy saving measures on the heat and electricity consumption

	Steam savings (10 ³ kg/h)	Electricity savings (kW)
The pressure regulation in fibre refining	0	43.3
The optimisation of stock mixing after refining	0	31.9
The use of hot water from adjacent compressor room	1.1	0

Results and discussion

The overall impact of presented energy audit recommendations are listed in Table VII. The annual operation time used in calculations was 8400 hours. In comparison with previous years, the reduction by 10.8 % in heat consumption and by 1.9 % in electric energy consumption was accomplished. Because of the character of proposed measures, no big investment was necessary. Therefore, economic rate of return was very low. More detailed feasibility studies are required for proper determination of economic and environmental benefits.

Table VII

Summarization of proposed energy savings proposals

	Steam saving (10 ³ kg/h)	Electricity saving (kW)	Annual heat saving (GJ)	Annual electricity saving (MWh)
Drying air ventilation adjustment	1.9	96	35000	810
Stock temperature increase	0.8 + 1.7 (winter)	0	22500	0
Other measures	1.1	75	20300	630
Sum	3.8 + 1.7 (winter)	171	77800	1440
Percent decrease in comparison with previous years			10.8	1.9

Conclusion

In this work, results of energy audit of a papermaking process were presented. Potential savings proposals were focused on steam savings and optimisation of electrical energy consumption in a paper machine. Reduction of more than 10 % in heat consumption and approximately 2 % in electricity consumption compared to energy consumption in previous years was achieved. The majority of measures consisted of only optimising the operation of technology and therefore no further investment was required. Consequently, economic rate of return calculated for proposed operation improvements was very low. The steam saved by increasing heat utilization efficiency was used for boosting the electricity production in the paper mill's central rating and power plant. The consequent lower overall electricity import of the paper mill led to a decrease of electricity production in a marginal source and subsequently to a reduction of global CO₂ emissions. Based on the presented results, proposed process optimisation by means of energy audit presents a feasible way in reducing carbon footprint of large chemical industry segments. Engineering approaches with lower degree of complexity can still in 21st century successfully contribute to sustainable development of chemical industry and reduction of its environmental burden.

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